

“Aurobindo And National Education Programme”

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The aim of education is always twofold: there is a collective aspect and there is an individual aspect. From the collective point of view, education is expected to turn the individual into a good citizen, i.e., into a person who has harmonious relations with the other members of the community, who is useful to the society and who fulfils with zeal his obligations as a citizen.

On the other hand, it may be expected that education will give to the individual a strong and healthy body, help him in building up his character and attaining self-mastery, and supply him with good opportunities of discovering and developing harmoniously his natural abilities.

It is often said that, as education is the building up of the thinking elite of the nation, much of the nation's future depends on its system of education. Artists and thinkers, saints and philosophers not by traders and politicians make Nations. National unity, integrity, and progress need a deeper foundation of cultural heritage, all time acceptable social harms, and value-system than political and economic arrangements. It is the life spirit that has shaped and unified our collective existence and has been the real bond of oneness among the Indian people. Indian culture is like a palimpsest in which new character does not entirely ignore the old. Indian culture is a living whole growing in richness and content with new ideas and philosophy. That is why it is evergreen ever young yet the oldest one. None of the culture in the entire world is so tolerant, all absorbing and assimilating but only and only the Indian culture. Primitive cultures are marked by extreme conservatism where social apathy of customs and convention with

irrational persistence living cultures are dynamic and maintain their cultural pattern by continuous efforts of individual and social discipline.

The roots of the ancient Indian system of education may be traced in the works of Vedic literature, namely the Vedic Sanhitas and the Upanishads. The main aim of the system is to train the mind to be an instrument of knowledge, not simply to fulfill with the knowledge. Indian education is ancient times endeavored to prepare humanity for the enlightenment of its consciousness. The core of purity and truth is available in our traditional values, yet we have permitted it to deteriorate due to our attraction to false value.

In the modern India too there have been many original thinkers on education, who have felt the need for a review of the educational system introduced by British rule, creating loyal servants of the government. There was a search for after system of education in the country among the reformers and intellectuals. In this process a good deal of thinking, combined with actual experimentation on various alternative models of education had taken place unfortunately, their contributions have not been adequately reflected in the educational decisions of Sri Aurobindo, Maharshi Dayanand Saraswati, Gurudeve R.N. Tagore, Dr. Zakir Hussain, Radhakrishnan and above all Mahatma Gandhi. It is high time to review the principles of education expounded by them and to examine their vitality in the present context.

Today's education is based on competition among individuals, which eventually propagates an attitude of violence within the self and with others. Real educational ideas get lost in self interested pursuits in which very little attention is paid to designs for a better world based upon improved relationship. One has to reflect on how education can be put back on the tracks of Taxila and Nalanda,

which brought forth unique creative ideas for the refinement of the human being. Their entire thrust was to create not just an intellectual instrument, but also an improved faculty of knowledge in man giving him an opportunity to deeply know about himself and his environment.

The problem of education is becoming deeper and broader every day as the world moves on. The watchword and the essence have been preached in the day of yore when the Vedantic truth was first discovered, the solidarity of all life. One atom cannot in this universe move without dragging in the whole world.

An introspection concerning our educational system creates a feeling the enduring philosophical ideas passed on by our eminent thinkers call for a careful review. Relinking ourselves with this valuable legacy will give us the sense of direction in molding our educational outlook.

Education has the dual function of transmitting to the new generation the heritage of the past with its accumulated wisdom and preparing it for the present and the future that the emergent need of society and individuals hold before us. Every education system is a living reality whose goals, structure and contents are influenced by social-economic and cultural sources and also by the system's inherent dynamics. Keeping this in view we shall search for our national roots for a sound philosophy of education.

Today the time has come to give serious thought to the question of how to preserve humane values, how to lay down methods to reconcile ancient and modern values of Indian education, how to honestly and righteously channel youth's energy for social and national integration, how to make present education morally and spiritually effective in the light of the life and teachings of great men who have been the bases life and teachings of great men who have been the bases of higher values of faith and idealism.

Education lacks values. Today the time has come to give serious thought to the question of how to lay down methods to reconcile ancient and modern values of Indian education, how to honestly and righteously channel youth's energy for social and national integration, how to make present education morally and spiritually effective in the light of the life and teachings of great men who have been the basis of higher values of faith and idealism. We need to consider the goals of education conceived in relation to society and to individual, and also as general indicate of relevance of its contents as a set of principles and criteria. While we make realistic analysis of the present situation, we need to discuss the dynamics, the factors and constants that will in all probability act in the future. Also education needs to address the challenges posed by the world's present problems.

As regards the education introduced by the British Government in India, Lord Curzon in his convocation address delivered on 17th February 1900. Observed in parts, 'we teach you in your Indian colleges, and we examines you in the Indian universities upon subjects not merely conveyed to you in a foreign language, but representing foreign ideas and modes of thoughts. They are like an aero lit discharged into space from a distant planet or like exotic plants imported from some antipodean climate.' The Indian education was divorced from the living realities of Indian life. It was unnational or denational in outlook, character and consequences. Unfortunately it continued for nearly century.

To replace the aimless education system introduced by Macaulay, there come up several national leaders of repute with schemes of National Education. Lala Lajpat Rai, raised a cry for 'National', pointed out: *"The Mohammedan college of Aligarh, the Arya College at Lahore, the Hindu College at Banaras, all embodied the 'national' ideals of their founders limited and sectarian as they*

were at the time. Each professed to provide its own kind of national education; (Great Books on Indian Education, Volume, 11, page 17).” All these Institutions however were open to persons of all creeds, denominations and religions, but in the end they provide to be undistinguished the general cult of love for the country was concerned but otherwise openly sectarian National education needed a comprehensive outlook and also an atmosphere of proud and glowing patriotism to thrive.

Regrettably, even as late as 1967, the Diamond Jubilee Seminar Organized by the National Council of Education, Bengal, Could not reach a consensus about the definition of ‘National Education’. Today many Indians dedicated to the case of education feel that since the both of education is drifting still; it is high time we started searching our national roots for a philosophy of education. Raja Ram Mohan Roy was ‘The first man of new regenerated Indian’.

And Sri Aurobindo was one of the greatest educators whose educational philosophy swayed the masses of India as never before or since. By education he means that which offers the tools whereby one can live, *“for the divine, for the country, for oneself, and for others, and this must be the ideal in every school which calls itself national.”* The guiding principles of the philosophy of education of Sri Aurobindo was the awakening of man as a spiritual being. Indian nation is a living spirit and soul. The nation-soul revealed in Indians or Indian consciousness, is a perennial source of creative activity. Here national unity has always been held as complementary to world unity and peace. In search of our national roots we need to consider it from a broader perspective. There are some perennial values, unique to the people of this land, which stood Indian in good stead throughout its long history and also there are other temporal values. These values need special attention. Indian is our sacred motherland. It is only few years

ago we got independence after many years of slavery. The limited efforts of all Indians of all classes are how necessary to build up the nation and make India seated over the throne of world Guru again as in amount time. But in order to proceed with this task, it is essential to have a clear conception about the future of India. For example when an artist sits down to draw, his picture can be best if there exists in this mind a clear idea about the subject of his drawing. In the way, and engineer, before he begins to construct a building, would certainly want for a school, or a hospital, or for a government office, or a residence? Only then will he draw the plan and proceed to construct the building. Therefore, before laying our hands on the task of nation building, we have to draw in our minds a clear picture of the future India.

After attainment of independence attempts were made by the government for the material reconstruction of the country. Development of industry and agriculture was emphasized. To stand a cultural renaissance and to foster national integration a programme of educational reconstruction was launched. Now we have achieved an enormous quantitative expansion and qualitative improvement in the field of education. But the question is that 'In what form do we want to build India? As a nation, with gigantic military power? But that cannot be our ideal. It is obvious from several examples that no military power survives long. Wealth and prosperity we certainly need to alleviate the poverty of masses. But if we imagine that by mere wealth, all the problems would be solved, then we are mistaken. In western countries there is no end of wealth, but they have no peace. The boys and girls of those countries are wandering about helplessly even after getting pleasure of all types and all sorts of luxuries.

So, it is necessary to study the ancient history of India. It will make us clear how ancient India had acquired her prosperity and, along with the, had also shown that path of peace. To build the India great, we have to accept all those ideals that

made us great. And to this must be added the knowledge of pure science and of technology. Added the knowledge of pure science and of technology.

Sri Aurobindo is one of the greatest educators whose educational philosophy swayed the masses of India as never before or since. He dedicated his life for society and education to provide conditions for all men to travel towards divine perfection and to express the power, the harmony, the beauty and joy of self-realization. Aurobindo conceived of education as an instrument for the real working of the spirit in the mind and body of the individual and the nation. His thought of education that for the individual will make its one central object the growth of the soul and its power and possibilities, for the nation will keep first in view the preservation, strengthening and enrichment of the nation – soul and its Dharma (Virtue) and raise both into powers of the life and ascending mind and soul of humanity. And at no time will it lose sight of man's highest object, the awaking and development of his spiritual being (Ibid, P.16), A concept underlying the true and living integral education.

Aurobindo's philosophy of education is based on spiritual renaissance, practice of yoga and brahmacharya. According to him real education is that which provides a free and creative environment to the child and by developing his interests, creativity, mental, moral and aesthetic finally leads to the development of his powers. He himself writes:

“The chief aim of education should be to help the growing soul to draw out that in itself which is the best and make it perfect for a noble use.”